

A new species of the genus *Brookula* (Gastropoda, Seguenzioidea) from deep water of Cuba

Una nueva especie del género *Brookula* (Gastropoda, Seguenzioidea) de aguas profundas de Cuba

Raúl FERNÁNDEZ-GARCÉS*, Federico RUBIO** & Emilio ROLÁN***

Recibido el 20-XI-2017. Aceptado el 22-XI-2017

ABSTRACT

A new species of the genus *Brookula* Iredale, 1912 is described, collected in deep water North of Cuba. The new species is compared with other congeneric ones previously known.

RESUMEN

Se describe una nueva especie del género *Brookula* Iredale, 1912 de aguas profundas del Norte de Cuba, haciendo comparación con las especies congénéricas previamente conocidas.

INTRODUCTION

The species of the genus *Brookula* Iredale, 1912 are of very small size and most of them are living in very deep water. For these reasons its study is relatively recent.

The systematic position of the genus *Brookula* has varied from one author to another. IREDALE (1912) introduced the genus *Brookula* for species hitherto classified in *Cyclostrema*. WARÉN (1992) provisionally placed the genus in the trochid subfamily Eucyclinae; criteria that was followed by ABSALÃO, MIYIJI & PIMENTA (2001) and ABSALÃO & PIMENTA (2005). Other authors placed the genus in the family Liottiidae (e.g. FINLAY, 1924; POWELL, 1937, 1951, 1960) or in the family Skeneidae (= "Cyclostrematidae" of authors, non P.

Fischer, 1885) (THIELE, 1925; CLARKE, 1961; KAY, 1979; HICKMAN & MACLEAN, 1990; HIGO, CALOMON & GOTO, 1999; and ZELAYA, 2005). BOUCHET & ROCROI (2005) noted that the family Brookulidae Iredale & McMichael, 1962 has no diagnosis, being therefore an invalid name, not available nomenclaturally.

SCHWABE & ENGL (2008: 202) consider that none of the criteria used by ZELAYA, ABSALÃO & PIMENTA (2006) to separate *Brookula* from *Benthobrookula* is sufficiently well-founded to justify this separation into two genera.

KANO, CHIKYU & WARÉN (2009: 414) consider *Benthobrookula* Clarke, 1961 a confirmed member of Seguenzioidea and *Brookula* a plausible member of the group.

* Centro de Estudios Ambientales (CEAC), Cienfuegos, Cuba.

** Pintor Ribera, 4-16^a, 4693 Quart de Poblet, Valencia, Spain.

*** Museo de Historia Natural, Universidad de Santiago de Compostela, Parque Vista Alegre, Campus Norte, 15782 Santiago de Compostela, Spain.

In the Expedition in Cuban waters organized by the USA ship Weatherbird II between 10th and 25th of May 2017, one species of this genus was found and it is described in the present work.

Abbreviations
CIM-UH (Centro de Investigaciones Marinas, University of La Habana, Cuba)
MNCN Museo Nacional de Ciencias Naturales, Madrid

SYSTEMATICS

VETIGASTROPODA Salvini-Plawen, 1980
Superfamily SEGUENZIOIDEA Verrill, 1884
Family [unsigned]
Genus *Brookula* Iredale, 1912

Brookula Iredale, 1912: 219. [Type species by original designation: *Brookula stibarochila* Iredale, 1912: 220]. [Holotype photographed in CLARKE, 1961: pl.1, fig.5). A topotype is shown in WARÉN (1992, fig. 23)].

Diagnosis: See SCHWABE & ENGL, 2008.

Remarks: Species of the *Brookula* genus are mainly distributed in the oceans of the southern hemisphere; records for the northern hemisphere are only known from the Indian and Pacific oceans (SCHWABE & ENGL, 2008). Its bathymetric range extends from shallow

water to abyssal depth (GAGE & TYLER, 1991; SCHWABE & ENGL, 2008). Stratigraphic distribution: Miocene to Recent (FINLAY, 1924; SCHWABE & ENGL, 2008).

The new species described represents the northernmost report of the genus *Brookula* in the Atlantic Ocean and the first one for the Caribbean area.

Brookula murawskii spec. nov. (Figure 1A-F)

Type material: Holotype (Fig. 1A) in MNCN (15.05/200009) and one paratype (Fig. 1B) in CIM-UH.

Type locality: North of Cuba, SL750, 23.0984° N, 82.9843° W, 1455 m.

Etymology: The specific name is after Dr. Steven A. Murawski, of the University of South Florida, who was chief scientist of the expedition where the species was found.

Description: Shell very small (< 2 mm), globose-turbinate, thin, umbilicate, with inflated whorls. Protoconch with a large globose nucleus (about 300 µm) and ¼ of whorl after the nucleus; its surface covered by a very fine and irregular reticle, forming microscopic pits in a somewhat alveolar pattern. Teleoconch with 2 ½ whorls of rapid increase, rounded in profile, with prominent axial ribs (21 on the first whorl and about 26 on the second); these ribs, under high magnification can be seen to bear several minute axial riblets. Between 15-18 spiral cordlets can be seen, between the ribs and overrunning them. Umbilicus deep, not very wide, not delimited

from the rest of the abapical area, and with prominent spiral cords inside. Aperture very regularly rounded; peristome thin and continuous contacting only on a short distance with the previous whorl.

Holotype is 1.64 mm in height x 1.44 mm in diameter.

Habitat: Bathyal species dredged at 1455 m deep.

Distribution: Only known from the type locality.

Remarks: Some species of the genus *Brookula* are somewhat similar:

Brookula calypso (Melvill & Standen, 1912), described from Burdwood Bank (54°25'S, 057°32'W, 102 m) is very

Figure 1. *Brookula murawskii* spec. nov. A: holotipo, 1.64 mm in height, North of Cuba, 1455 m (MNCN); B: paratipo (CIM-UH); C, D: protoconch of the paratipo and detail; E, F: sculpture of the teleoconch and detail.

Figura 1. Brookula murawskii spec. nov. A: holotipo, 1,64 mm de altura, Norte de Cuba, 1455 m (MNCN); B: paratipo (CIM-UH); C, D: protoconcha del paratipo y detalle; E, F: escultura de la teleoconcha y detalle.

similar in size and outline. The protoconch, nevertheless, has a different sculpture of small granules (see ABSALÃO ET AL., 2001) instead of the micropitted structure found in the present species. Also, *B. calypso* has cords on the umbilical area and those do not extend inside the umbilicus.

Brookula megaumbilicata Absalão & Pimenta, 2005, is much more depressed, the protoconch is less than 200 μm in diameter and has a much more blurred microsculpture, the umbilicus is wider and has prominent lamellar axial ribs, and no cords inside.

Brookula conica (Watson, 1886) is also more depressed, the umbilicus also lacks the spiral riblets and instead has very strong axial ribs continued inside (ABSALÃO ET AL., 2001: fig. 2).

Brookula proseila Absalão & Pimenta, 2005 is slightly larger, with a somewhat smaller (260 μm) protoconch, the axial

ribs a little more prominent, the umbilicus is sharply delimited by a stronger spiral cord and the intraumbilical cordlets are very fine.

Brookula pfefferi Powell, 1951, and has more numerous axial ribs and a more irregular spiral sculpture, being the lower spiral cords very fine and closely set together, and few strong, widely spaced cords inside the umbilicus (ABSALÃO ET AL., 2001: fig. 3; ZELAYA ET AL., 2005: fig. 5).

Brookula spinulata Absalão, Miyaji & Pimenta, 2001 also has the lower spiral cords finer and closely set, is narrower in outline and has a narrower umbilicus sharply bound by a cord and nearly smooth inside.

Brookula olearia Absalão & Pimenta, 2005 is smaller, more depressed with a more globose outline, the spiral cordlets are very nodulous, and the umbilicus is delimited by a strong spiral cord.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors thank the expedition leader Dr. Steven A. Murawski (University of South Florida (USF)), Dr. Maickel Armenteros Almanza (Centro de Investigaciones Marinas, University of La Habana (CIM-UH)), and the Centro de Estudios Ambientales de

Cienfuegos (CEAC), participant on behalf of Cienfuegos province in the collecting of sediment. Jesús Méndez of the Centro de Apoyo Científico y Tecnológico a la Investigación (CACTI) of the University of Vigo made the SEM micrographs.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- ABSALÃO R.S., MIYAJI C. & PIMENTA A.D. 2001. The genus *Brookula* Iredale, 1912 (Gastropoda, Trochidae) from Brazil: description of a new species, with notes on other South American species. *Zoosystema*, 23 (4): 675-687.
- ABSALÃO R.S. & PIMENTA A.D. 2005. New records and new species of *Vetulonia* Dall, 1913 and *Brookula* Iredale, 1912 from Brazil (Gastropoda, Trochidae). *The Veliger*, 47 (3): 193-201.
- BOUCHET P. & ROCROI J.-P. 2005. Classification and Nomenclator of Gastropod Families. *Malacologia*, 47 (1-2): 1-397 pp.
- CLARKE A.H. 1961. Moluscos abisales del Océano Atlántico Sur. *Boletín del Museo de Zoología Comparativa*, 4: 345-387.
- FINLAY H.J. 1924. The family Liottiidae, Iredale, in the New Zealand Tertiary: Part 1. The genus *Brookula*. *Transactions and Proceedings of the Royal Society of New Zealand*, 55, 526-531, pl. 53.
- GAGE J.D. & TYLER P.A. 1991. *Deep-sea biology: a natural history of organisms at the deep-sea*, floor xvi, 504 pp. Cambridge University Press.
- HICKMAN R. & MCLEAN J. 1990. Systematic revision and suprageneric classification of trochacean gastropods. *Science Series, Natural History Museum of Los Angeles County*, 35: 1-169.
- HIGO S., CALLOMON P. & GOTO, Y. 1999. *Catalogue and bibliography of the marine shell-bearing Mollusca of Japan*. Elle Scientific Publications, Osaka, pp. 749.

- IREDALE, T. 1912. New generic names and new species of marine Mollusca. *Proceedings of the Malacological Society of London*, 10: 217–228, pl. 9.
- KANO Y. 2008. Vetigastropod phylogeny and a new concept of Seguenzioidea: independent evolution of copulatory organs in the deep-sea habitats. *Zoologica Scripta*, 37: 1–21.
- KANO Y., CHIKYU E. & WARÉN A. 2009. Morphological, Ecological and Molecular characterization of the enigmatic planispiral snail genus *Adeuomphalus* (Vetigastropoda, Seguenzioidea). *Journal of Molluscan Studies*, 75: 397–418.
- KAY E.A. 1979. Hawaiian marine shells: Reef and shore fauna of Hawaii. Section 4: Mollusca. *Bernice P. Bishop Museum Special Publication*, 64 (4): 1–653.
- POWELL A.W.B. 1937. New species of marine Mollusca from New Zealand. *Discovery Reports*, 15: 153–222, pls. 45–56.
- POWELL A.W.B. 1951. Antarctic and Subantarctic Mollusca: Pelecypoda and Gastropoda. *Discovery Reports*, 26: 47–196.
- POWELL A.W.B. 1960. Antarctic and subantarctic Mollusca. *Records of the Auckland Institute and Museum*, 5 (3–4): 117–193.
- POWELL A.W.B. 1979. *New Zealand Mollusca. Marine, Land and Freshwater Shells*, William Collins Publishers Ltd, Auckland, i–xiv, 500 pp.
- SCHWABE E. & ENGL W. 2008. Description of two new deep-water species of the genus *Brookula* Iredale, 1912 (Mollusca, Gastropoda, Trochoidea), with a revision of the genus for the Subantarctic and Arctic Sector of the Atlantic Ocean. *Zootaxa*, 1866: 187–204.
- THIELE A. 1925. Gastropoda der Deutschen Tiefsee-Expedition. II. Teil. *Wissenschaftliche Ergebnisse der Deutschen Tiefsee-Expedition auf dem Dampfer "Valdivia" 1898-1899*, 17 (2): 35–382, pls. 13–46.
- WARÉN A. 1992. New and little known "Skeineimorph" gastropods from the Mediterranean Sea and the adjacent Atlantic Ocean. *Bollettino Malacologico*, 27 (10-12): 149–248.
- ZELAYA D.G. 2005. Systematics and biogeography of marine gastropod molluscs from South Georgia. *Spixiana*, 28 (2): 109–139.
- ZELAYA D.G., ABSALÃO R.S. & PIMENTA A.D. 2006. A revision of *Benthobrookula* Clarke, 1961 (Gastropoda, Trochoidea) in the Southwestern Atlantic Ocean. *Journal of Molluscan Studies*, 72: 77–87.

